

STUDY ON ELECTROMAGNETIC CHARACTERISTICS FOR DEVELOPMENT OF MICROWAVE MEDICAL IMAGING SYSTEM.

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Resumo - The work consists of a detailed study carried out on the characteristics of the development of a microwave medical imaging system (MMIS) and aims to understand its operation. The scope of this work comprises the electrical characteristics of healthy and malignant biological tissues, the dielectric characteristics of the human chest region, the interactions of electromagnetic waves (EWs) with tissues, as well as the functioning of the MMIS and the emission/repetition of electromagnetic signals. As a result, it was found that malignant tissues have a higher dielectric constant, which generates greater reflection intensity and that there is a need to process the reflected signals, which arrive full of noise, to synthesize the image using frequencies in the microwave range.

Palavras-chave: Dielectrics in Biological Tissue; Electromagnetic Reflection, Interaction of Electromagnetic Waves with Tissues; Antenna Radiation, Monostatic Radar.

INTRODUCTION

Ultra-wideband (UWB) systems, which use non-ionizing electromagnetic waves, can synthesize medical images for pre-diagnosis in the detection of tumors [1]-[4], emerging as a safe, low-cost [4], [5], non-invasive [6] alternative that can have compact dimensions [7], allowing patients who are unable to move around and have difficulty performing other types of imaging examination have access to microwave medical imaging systems (MMIS). Furthermore, the smaller dimensions and lower costs can popularize MMISs so that, for example, they can be used in basic health units, enabling broad access for society in the event of the need for an imaging examination.

MMISs have, as one of the main elements, one or more antennas, glued or not to the patient's body [7], for emission and reception of electromagnetic waves (EW) that are radiated in the direction of the region to be evaluated and captures the EW reflected. The reflected signals are received with incorporated noise, generating the need for signal processing [5], [8]. The treatment is carried out using algorithms capable of processing this data and synthesizing the image of a possible target (Tumor or Infection), as seen in the works of [9] and [10]. This identification of the target is possible, as diseased and healthy tissues have different dielectric constants (ϵ), and in patients, the constants are greater than in healthy ones [8]. This electrical property of biological tissues generates differentiated contrasts through microwave interactions that enable the generation of images of tumors, hemorrhages or infections [1]-[3], [9], [11], [12].

That said, the objective of the authors of this work is to present a study on the characteristics that are taken into consideration for MMIS development.

ELECTRICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF BIOLOGICAL TISSUE

The principle of medical imaging using microwave radar is based on the difference in the dielectric constant of healthy and malignant biological

tissue [4], [8], where the healthy one has a much lower constant than the malignant one [13]. This is visualized through the reflections of EW [8] in which the reflection coefficient increases close to the tumor [1], thus making detection possible [14].

Each biological tissue has inherent dielectric properties [15] that vary with frequency and temperature [16]. For higher frequencies, there is a decrease in ϵ and an increase in the conductivity of the tissue that is interacting with the EW [6], [7], [15], as shown in the graph in Figure 1 of the lung inflated with air to illustrate [17]. The variation in ϵ and conductivity is related to the polarization of molecules and structural interfaces in response to the 38 electromagnetic fields [13]. Another factor that can influence the dielectric properties of biological tissues is the amount of water and the composition of the cells [16].

Figure 1 – Relationship of frequency with the dielectric constant and conductivity of the lung inflated with air. [50].

DIELECTRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE LUNG AND TUMORS

The dielectric properties of benign tumors have a ϵ lower than cancerous ones but higher than healthy tissues and this is because the malignant one has a different membrane composition, with a higher concentration of relevant ions, proteins and water [15], in addition to a higher concentration of sodium that helps with the accumulation of liquid [13]. Other factors such as patient age [15] and tumor stage modify and influence the dielectric constant of tumors [13].

The lungs are located in the region of the chest that has different tissues, such as skin, fat, muscle, ribs (bones) and the lung itself. Each of these tissues has its own dielectric constant, with that of the lung being

variable and changing in the dynamic movement of breathing [4], as it is in this breathing process that there is a thinning of the alveolar walls, deformation of the epithelial cells and blood vessels of so that ϵ is inversely proportional to the amount of air in the lung [6].

Figure 2, based on the database provided by [17], presents a planar model of the chest region where the lungs are located with their different layers and their respective ϵ subjected to a frequency of 2.45 GHz and room temperature.

Figure 2 – Planar model of the thorax with its different layers. [50].

MMIS OPERATION

The lung region has several biological tissues and each one has its own dielectric constant, as does the foreign body (tumor/infection), whose constant is much higher than healthy ones. When interacting with the EW, the signals reflected and captured by the MMIS Antenna are backscattered due to the different tissues [5]. For effective EW penetration [4], a low-frequency application is suggested. In work [11], a frequency of 3.0 GHz was used, whereas [13] used the range from 1.0 to 3.0 GHz, while [7] suggests a range from 0.5 to 1.5 GHz. Low frequencies reduce image resolution, while high frequencies reduce the penetration of EWs into biological tissues [7]. Therefore, these bands mentioned above can help in defining frequencies for use in these types of microwave imaging systems.

To transmit and receive backscattered signals that are weak and in disorder, there is a need to process these indices to reconstruct an image that detects tumors [4], [8]. For this purpose, it is possible to use different microwave imaging systems that are classified as monostatic (uses a single antenna to transmit and capture the reflected signals) and multistatic (uses one antenna to transmit the electromagnetic waves and another to capture or antenna array). In both systems, the antenna (s) can be glued to the patient's body or kept at small distances from the body. These systems must follow rules for Specific Absorption Rate (SAR), considering the body's energy absorption limitations in which the distance from the antenna to the body interferes, as well as the frequency used. At low frequencies, there are deeper penetrations, resulting, therefore, in a higher SAR [7].

Figure 3 shows a flow of how a monostatic MMIS works, which has one element, VNA, which measures reflections and is connected by coaxial cable to the antenna, which captures and radiates electromagnetic waves, and to the computer by USB cable, which uses a signal processing to treat backscattered signals and present the image in a synthesized form. This element is the algorithm developed in software together with the computer's processing capacity.

Figure 3 – Flow of a monostatic microwave imaging system.

The monostatic one presented in this work is easy to implement and uses fewer devices than the multistatic ones, in addition to having a faster scanning time without compromising image quality.

CONCLUSION

The interaction of electromagnetic waves between healthy and malignant biological tissues is an important condition for generating images at the microwave frequency, but not the only one, as it is necessary to treat the signals reflected by the tissues that are captured by the (s) antenna(s), precisely to remove embedded noise. Therefore, a set of factors must be taken into consideration for the development of the MMIS, from the object to be detected as well as its electrical characteristics, in addition to the antenna that must be directive and the processing of backscattered signals captured to synthesize an image using a band of microwaves.

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